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MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

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ECOSYSTEM HEALTH ASSESSMENT OF THE KARST LANDSCAPE OF
BORACAY ISLAND BASED ON SPATIO-TEMPORAL CHANGES OF
LANDSCAPE

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6 January 2024

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface
- II. Due to acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

LAILA GRACE ROXAN B. INDICO

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ABSTRACT

Assessment of ecosystem health, especially in fragile and vulnerable environment, such as that of karst landscapes is essential in protecting these landscapes. This provides an indispensable reference in the formulation of a more appropriate protection policies in order to maintain healthy ecosystems or reverse those that have unhealthy levels of ecosystem health. This study assessed the spatial and temporal changes of the ecosystem health of Boracay through remote sensing images, such as that of Landsat developed by NASA and USGS, using the parameters of VOR framework developed by Costanza (1992), such as ecosystem vigor, ecosystem organization, and ecosystem resilience. The results show that the ecosystem health of Boracay Island declined over time, from 1989 to 2020. The ecosystem health evolved from suboptimal healthy landscape in 1989 for the three barangays of the island to average health up to a degraded landscape in 2020. The level of ecosystem health relates to the effects of development due to tourism growth in the island wherein less fragmented, more aggregated, less complex portions have an average healthy ecosystem at 2020 while the portions that are highly fragmented, less aggregated, more complex and sprawled by development corresponds to unhealthy to degraded level of ecosystem health. This study provides a cost-effective, scientific basis in the assessment and even monitoring of ecosystem health for environmental managers and local government units in the formulation of sustainable management policies and activities of other tourism sites in the country.

Keywords: *Ecosystem health; Boracay Island; VOR framework; Landscape structure*

I. INTRODUCTION

Ecosystems provide goods and services for human survival and development and, as such a healthy ecosystem assures these for sustainable social, cultural, and economic development (Wang et al., 2022). However, due to increasing pressures that ecosystems are continuously exposed to such as rapid population growth (Ge et al., 2022), urbanization and industrialization (Wang et al., 2022), habitat fragmentation, and global warming (Li et al., 2023), these have led to the unprecedented changes in ecosystems at the global scale that caused degradation of the environment and its services (Wangf et al., 2022). This poses a threat to the sustainable development and survival of human society.

People travel to places to explore, go on adventures and meet people, interact with them, discovering their culture, values, and tradition (Baloch et al., 2023) has driven high tourism growth at present and is one of fastest-growing industries, contributing more than 10% to the global GDP (UNWTO, 2020). With its growth, there are positive effects on employment, wealth generation, and economy, but also brought environmental pollution and degradation at tourist destinations (Baloch et al., 2023). The exploitation of the natural ecosystems hastened such as more forestlands are converted to urbanized areas. This was done at the expense of the environment and the resources therein, such as the biophysical resources and the accompanying social and cultural resources with it (Xiang et al., 2019). Moreover, Xiang et al (2019) pointed out that in the recent millennia, the destruction and disruption of tourist destination through built-up sprawling have been increasing and have been affecting ecosystem balance and landscape sustainability.

Most of tourist destinations are often in karst landscapes (Vorlaufer, 2005). Karst landscapes are those areas that have distinct landforms and hydrology as a result of “*combination of high rock solubility and consequently well-developed secondary porosity*” (Ford and Williams, 2007 in He et al., 2021). These landscapes consist of surface and subsurface geologic features that were formed by the action of groundwater, such as caves, sinkholes, springs and disappearing streams. Karst areas have characteristically “*small population capacity, simple community structure, high environmental sensitivity, weak disaster bearing capacity, and difficulty in recovery*” (Zhao et al., 2021). Due to these, karst areas are considered as one of the most fragile and vulnerable ecosystems in the world (Chen et al., 2016; Brinkmann and Parise, 2012). The Philippines has an extensive karst landscape covering 35,000 square kilometers of the archipelago (BMB, n.d.). This is approximately 11.7% of the countries’ total land area. Most of the country’s top tourism sites are set in karst areas, such as the *Boracay Island, Siargao, Puerto Princesa Underground River, Mountain Province, and Coron* to name a few. These areas have experienced rapid development brought by influx of tourists, causing more lands converted to accommodate construction of hotels and other tourist amenities.

Ecosystem health is the ability of the natural ecosystems to self-manage such as organize, maintain, and recover from any disturbance caused by both natural and anthropogenic activities which is important in the survival and development of the human society (Li et al., 2023). According to Costanza et al (1992), a healthy ecosystem is defined by vigor which is the ecosystems activity and primary productivity, organization which is the diversity and interactions of ecosystems, and resilience which is the capability of the ecosystem to maintain its structure and function when subjected to stress. Assessment of ecosystem health has become a new interest

for environmental researches (Lei et al., 2023). This provides basis for ecological restoration and environmental management (Chen et al., 2016). Ecosystem consists interrelationships that are highly complex (Wang et al., 2020). Several index framework models and multicriteria-based evaluation models were established to measure ecosystem health of complex ecosystems, such as index of biotic integrity, direct measurement method (DMM), ecological modelling method (EMM), pressure-state-response (PSR) model proposed by the OECD in 1993 (Fu et al., 2021), analytic hierarchy process (AHP) model, vitality organization resilience (VOR) developed by Costanza et al (1992), driving force state response (DSR), and Driving Force Pressure State Impact Response (DPSIR) (Wang et al., 2020, Wang et al., 2020). Among these, VOR model has been widely used due to its simplicity and ability to express complex phenomena into linear scale (Das et al., 2020).

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ecosystem health assessment is a relatively new method in environmental management (Costanza, 2012) but due its relevance has become a new interest and direction of environmental research (Lei et al., 2023). Achieving and maintaining a healthy ecosystem has been the primary goal of ecological restoration and environmental management (Chen et al., 2016). The concept on ecosystem health was first proposed by Rapport et al in 1985 which had its main focus on ecosystem stability and sustainability. In 1992, Costanza defined it as the ability of natural systems to keep its organizational structure, able to respond to changing conditions, and recover from stressors (Lei et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2020). Costanza et al (1992) also emphasized that the concept of a healthy ecosystem acknowledges the fact that humans are a major component of most of ecosystem and are at the receiving end of the services offered by ecosystems. Based on these, he developed categories of performance that are associated with the well-functioning of any living system at any scale. These categories are *vigor*, *organization*, and *resilience* (Contanza, 1992).

Ecosystem is comprised of multiple interactive relationships that are highly complex (Wang et al., 2020). The two main methods in assessing ecosystem health are (1) indicator species method/biological indicator method and (2) index method (Wang et al., 2020; Phillips et al., 2022; Kong et al., 2002). Indicator species method is based on the number of dominant species, key species, and sensitive species in the community in order to analyze the environmental changes and assess the health of the natural ecosystems (Fu et al., 2021). On the other hand, the index method is used for the study of composite ecosystems (Ge et al., 2022). It integrates large amount of complex information and combines disciplines, such as from biochemistry, ecology,

economics, and others to filter out appropriate comprehensive metrics, establish an index system, and assess the ecosystem health (Fu et al., 2021; Rapport 2011). Several index framework models and multicriteria-based evaluation models were established to measure ecosystem health, such as index of biotic integrity, direct measurement method (DMM), ecological modelling method (EMM), pressure-state-response (PSR) model proposed by the OECD in 1993 (Fu et al., 2021), analytic hierarchy process (AHP) model, vitality organization resilience (VOR) developed by Costanza et al (1992), driving force state response (DSR), and Driving Force Pressure State Impact Response (DPSIR) (Wang et al., 2020, Wang et al., 2020).

Among these index models, VOR has been widely used for ecosystem health assessment. VOR model proposed by Costanza et al (1992) is based on landscape structure and quantitatively assess ecosystem health based on the system health formula that uses ecosystem vigor (EV), ecosystem organization (EO), and ecosystem resilience (ER) (Wang et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Li et al., 2023; Lei et al., 2023; Costanza, 2012). The VOR model has been widely used because of the simplicity of its calculation process and able to express complex concepts of ecosystem health into a linear scale ranging from 0 to 1, where 0 represents the “weakest” EH and 1 represents the “best” EH (Das et al., 2020). Ecosystem Health is calculated as follow (Li et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022):

$$EHI = \sqrt[3]{EV \times EO \times ER}$$

Table 1

Classification of ecosystem health adapted from Chen et al (2016) and Lei et al (2023)

Classification Standard	Index Value	Characteristics of the ecosystem
Highest Health	0.8 to 1.0	High level of structural integrity, stability, and sustainability; perfect ecological function; non or nearly no negative impact from external human and/or non-human factors; no abnormalities; high resilience
Suboptimal Health	0.6 to 0.8	Moderate level of structural integrity, stability, and sustainability; high ecological function; slightly negative impact from external human and/or non-human factors; no abnormalities; moderate resilience
Average Health	0.4 to 0.6	Marginal level of structural integrity, stability, and sustainability; degraded ecological functioning; noticeable levels of human disturbance; low resilience
Unhealthy	0.2 to 0.4	Low level of structural integrity, stability, and sustainability; degraded ecological functioning; significant human disturbance; low resilience
Degraded	0 to 0.2	Extremely poor structural integrity, stability, and sustainability; highly degraded

		ecological functioning; severe human disturbance; very low resilience
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Ecosystem Vigor (EV)

Ecosystem vigor is the measure of activity and metabolism or primary productivity. It is the ecological metabolism and nutrient recycling capacity of an ecosystem (Chen et al., 2016; Ge et al., 2022). It is determined from the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI). NDVI has been significantly correlated to primary productivity, and as such, generally been used to measure ecosystem vigor (Wang et al., 2022). The range of NDVI is [-1, 1], where the closer absolute value to 1 has the greatest EV (Li et al., 2023). The formula for calculating NDVI is:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - R}{NIR + R}$$

Where NIR and R are the fourth and third bands, respectively, of Landsat TM images and fourth and fifth bands, respectively, of Landsat OLI images (Wang et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023).

Ecosystem Organization (EO)

Ecosystem organization refers to the number and diversity of interaction between the components of a system. It describes the stability and complexity of the ecosystem structure and is mainly reflected in the diversity of the natural landscape and impact of human activities (Wang et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023). It is measured using landscape indices related to heterogeneity, connectivity, and shape. For landscape heterogeneity (LH), Shannon diversity index (SHDI) and

Shannon evenness index (SHEI) are used. For landscape connectivity (LC), aggregation index (AI), cohesion index (COHESION), contagion index (CONTAG), and landscape division index (DIVISION) are used. To assess landscape shape (LS), area-weighted mean fractal index (AWFDI) and area weighted mean shape index (AWMSI) are used. The weight for each index will be assigned using analytical hierarchy process. In general, EO is calculated by the following formula (Lei et al., 2023):

$$EO = \sum_{i=1}^n Wi \times Xi$$

Where *EO* is the ecosystem organization, *n* represents the number of indicators, *Xi* standardized landscape metric, and *Wi* is the weight of the indicator.

Table 2

Landscape pattern indices and their ecological significance

Landscape Index	Ecological Significance
Shannon Diversity Index (SHDI)	This metric mainly emphasizes the richness aspect of diversity. In the study conducted by Karimi and Raymond (2022), they used the Shannon Diversity Index (together with the evenness index) to examine the spatial patterns of perceived ecosystem services, e.g., the number of ecosystem service types and features of the landscape, at the landscape scale.

			<p>The use of this metric, in conjunction with the evenness metric, allows the proponent to quantify the richness aspect of diversity by examining the number of ecosystem service types (Raymond and Karimi, 2022).</p>
	Shannon Evenness Index (SHEI)		<p>Value ranges from 0 to 1. When SHEI is small, dominance degree is generally high which means that the landscape is dominated by one or few patch type. When SHEI approaches to 1, dominance is low meaning that no patch type dominates the landscape and each patch type is evenly distributed within the landscape.</p> <p>The evenness metric examines the equitability in the abundances of the mapped ecosystem services (Karimi and Raymond, 2022).</p>
Landscape Connectivity	Aggregation Index (AI)		It is the degree of aggregation of the landscape or a patch type
	Cohesion Index (COHESION)		It is the physical connectedness of the focal patch type. Cohesion approaches 0 when the focal class decreases and

		becomes increasingly divided and less connected.
	Contagion Index (CONTAG)	It describes the degree of clustering or the tendency of different patch types to spread across the landscape
	Landscape Division Index (DIVISION)	Degree of aggregation within a landscape. DIVISION is 0 when the landscape consists of a single patch. It approaches to 1 when the focal patch type decreases and as those patches decreases in size.
Landscape Shape	Area-Weighted Mean Fractal Index (FRAC_AM)	This is a metric for shape complexity adjusted for the shape size. Because larger patch types tend to be more complex than smaller patch types, this determines the patch complexity independent of its size.
	Area Weighted Mean Shape Index (SHAPE_AM)	It equals the average shape index of patches of the corresponding patch type, weighted by patch area so that larger patches weigh more than smaller patches.

Note: Adapted from MacGarigal and Marks, 1995; Wang et al., 2023; Lei et al., 2023

Ecosystem Resilience (ER)

Ecosystem resilience is the ability to maintain the system's structure and pattern of behavior in the presence of a stressor (Costanza, 2012). It is the capacity of the ecosystem to recover from external disturbances (Li et al., 2023). Land use/land cover is an indispensable influence on ecosystem recovery and so, to measure ER, the sum of the area-weighted ecosystem resilience coefficients for all the land use/land cover types are measured (He et al., 2019). Therefore, ecosystem resilience is calculated for each land use based on Wang et al (2020) as:

$$ER = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i \times RC_i$$

where A_i is the area ratio of ecosystem type i and RC_i is the resilience coefficient of ecosystem type i , and n is the number of ecosystem type.

Table 3

Ecosystem resilience coefficient (RC) of each ecosystem type

Ecosystem type	RC
Built-up zone	0.2
Forestland	0.6
Waterbody (Wetlands, Beach)	0.7

Note: Based from He et al (2019), Wang et al (2020), Wang et al (2022), and Li et al (2023).

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

Ecosystems provide a plethora of services to society in the form of provisioning, regulating, supporting, and cultural services. However, with increase in population, urbanization, and land conversion, these services are affected and thus, the ecosystem health. Boracay Island is known as a top tourist destination in the Philippines. With this, the island had undergone development, since the early years of tourism until the present. Boracay Island is also a karst landscape, i.e., its inherent features are formed by dissolution of its underlying lithology. Karst areas are considered to be one of the most fragile and vulnerable ecosystems in the world (Chen et al., 2016; Brinkmann and Parise, 2012). The changes that Boracay Island undergone have effects on the health of the landscape, such as whether it is still able to organize, maintain, and recover from disturbances, either natural or man-made. This study will assess the spatio-temporal changes of the ecosystem health of the karst landscape of Boracay Island using Landsat images taken at different time periods (1989, 2000, 2018, 2020) using the vigor-organization-resilience (VOR) framework developed by Costanza (1992). Using VOR framework, each parameter will be determined, such as ecosystem vigor will be computed from the NDVI of Landsat images, ecosystem organization from the landscape pattern of Boracay, and ecosystem resilience from the areas of the ecosystems comprising Boracay Island and the resilience coefficient of the land cover type.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE SUDY

This study proposes to assess the ecosystem health of Boracay Island, one of the country's top tourist destinations and has recently undergone rehabilitation initiatives. Specifically, this aims to:

- a) Determine the spatio-temporal changes in the landscape structure of Boracay Island;
- b) Analyze the spatio-temporal changes in ecosystem health of the island using VOR method of ecosystem health proposed by Constanza (1992); and
- c) Analyze the relationship between the changes in the landscape structure of Boracay Island and its ecosystem health index.

The result from this study can provide additional science-based information in updating the Boracay Action Plan to improve management and recommend strategies to preserve the remaining ecosystems in Boracay Island for achieving sustainable tourism in the island.

V. RATIONALE

The exploitation of the karst areas drives changes in their landscape resulting to adverse ecological effects, such as habitat fragmentation (Abera et al., 2021), climate warming (Pan et al., 2020), and even subsidence. Faced with these challenges on environment and natural resource utilization, researches on assessing and monitoring ecosystem health, especially of a vulnerable and fragile karst landscape, has been increasingly studied (Li et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2016).

Assessment of ecosystem health in karst areas is a prerequisite in any ecological restoration and sustainable development (Chen et al., 2016). It has been done in other countries but not in the Philippines. This study will provide an initial system for assessing the ecosystem health of tourist destinations in karst landscapes in the country to inform management, restoration and rehabilitation efforts.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATION

The scope of the study will be on the assessment of ecosystem health of the landscape of Boracay Island using the Vigor-Organization-Resilience (VOR), which employs the ecosystem vigor from NDVI, ecosystem organization from landscape metrics, and ecosystem resilience from landscape metrics and resilience coefficient of land cover types, model developed by Constanza (1992) based on landscape configuration and metrics. Landscape metrics will be processed from Landsat images taken at different time periods, such as 1989, 2000, 2018, and 2020.

The study is limited only on the use of remote sensing images to assess ecosystem health and to develop and compute NDVI from, land cover configuration, and landscape metrics. Moreover, parameter constants are derived from previous studies conducted on ecosystem health.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

Boracay Island is located at the northwestern tip of Panay Island in the Municipality of Malay, Province of Aklan, specifically between the geographic coordinates of 11° 57' – 12° 00' latitudes and 121° 56' – 121° 57' (Lustica et al., 2009). Its landmass measures approximately 6.8 kilometers by 3.3 kilometers, at widest point, and has a highest elevation of 105 meters above mean sea level. The whole island of Boracay is underlain by Plio-Pleistocene limestone of Libertad Formation and Quaternary Alluvium derived from the underlying limestone formation (Peña and Aurelio, 2004).

Boracay Island is a biodiversity haven before rapid development has taken place during 1990s (BIATF, 2019). It has a rich set of interacting ecosystems comprised of mangrove flats, coral reefs, wetlands, marshlands, lagoons, and forestlands (BIATF, 2019). The island is inhabited by *Malaynon* locals and *Ati* tribe dependent on fishing and small-scale agriculture in the 60's (Lustica et al., 2009). Tourism in the island started in the 70's with *nipa* huts as accommodation and kerosene lamps as lighting during the night (BIATF, 2019). During that time, Boracay Island served as a low budget destination for backpacking tourists who sought for a simple and laid-back vacation experience (BIATF, 2019).

Boracay Island has undergone a very rapid development as a premiere ecotourism destination. At present, it provides amenities from low budget travels to high-end accommodations and various activities. Millions of foreign and local tourists flocked the island because of its 4-kilometer-long white sand beach, crystal blue waters (BIATF, 2019), numerous inland and offshore island activities, and vibrant night life.

Tourism in the island prompted an annual tourist arrival that have ballooned from 14,000 in 1984 to 634,263 in 2008 to more than 2 million in 2017 and the population in the island have grown from 9001 in 1995 to 18,229 in 2007 to 56,444 in 2018 (Lustica et al., 2009; BIATF, 2019). The growth of the island was already foreseen in the early 2000s, thus then President Gloria Macapagal Arroyo, through Presidential Proclamation No. 1064, reclassified Boracay into forestland (377.06 hectares or 38%) for protection purposes and alienable and disposable lands (628.96 hectares or 62%) for agricultural purposes (BIATF, 2019). Despite of this, encroachment of structures and conversion of forestlands in Boracay still continues.

This unprecedented growth had resulted into high level of fecal coliform in *Bulabog* Beach and White Beach due to illegal pipes draining to these bodies of water causing a decline in coral cover, insufficient sewage treatment plant, and ultimately, encroachment of structures in forestlands and wetlands.

Figure 1. Location map of Boracay Island (circled in red), Malay, Aklan. *Data source:* Administrative boundary from Philippine Statistics Authority

Figure 2. Nipa huts served as accommodations during the early years of tourism in Boracay Island (Gomez, 2019).

Figure 3. Landscape of Boracay Island taken last 2018. (Upper photo) View looking south to Brgys. Balabag and Manocmanoc; (Below photo) View looking north to Brgy. Yapak.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

The ecosystem health assessment of the karst landscape of Boracay Island, Malay, Aklan used the vigor-organization-resilience (VOR) framework developed by Costanza et al (1992) that is based on landscape pattern analysis to quantitatively assess the ecosystem health. Below is the framework of the methodology employed:

Figure 4. Methodology on the ecosystem health assessment of the karst landscape of Boracay Island, Malay, Aklan, Philippines.

Data Sources and Processing

The basic data of this study are the LANDSAT images, developed and launched by the US Department of Interior, Department of Agriculture, and NASA (Landsat Missions, n.d.). Satellite images from different time periods are acquired, from the early years of tourism in Boracay up until present: 1989, 2000, 2009, 2018, and 2020. The images are to be downloaded using the Semi-Automatic Classification Plugin in QGIS. The datasets are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 4

Landsat Images Acquired using the SCP Plugin in QGIS

Sensor Details	Date Acquired	Resolution
Landsat 5 TM	July 5, 1989	30 m
Landsat 7 ETM+	August 12, 2000	30 m / 15 m
Landsat 8 OLI	November 11, 2018	30 m / 15 m
	November 15, 2020	30 m / 15 m

Spatio-temporal analysis of the land cover of Boracay Island

The land cover for each dataset was analyzed using Unsupervised Classification in Semi-Automatic Classification Plugin (Congedo, 2021) of QGIS 3.16.11 (QGIS Development Team, 2021). Unsupervised classification categorizes raster data into discrete thematic groups having the same spectral-radiometric signatures/values then the computer provides statistical calculations based on the signature files and assigns each pixel or grid the class it closely resembles to (Image Classification Unsupervised, 2016). Clustering using ISODATA algorithm was employed for the unsupervised classification. Clustering using ISODATA merges clusters having similar spectral signatures and splits clusters having too much variability (Congedo, 2021). The ISODATA parameters used include: distance

threshold of 0.01 with 15 as number classes, ISODATA max standard deviation of 0.2 with 15 as ISODATA minimum class size in pixels, and seed signature used random and at minimum distance. Each of the 14/15 cluster values at singleband pseudocolor equal interval were categorized as either vegetation (trees/vegetation-covered wetlands), water (coastal water, wetland), and built-up areas (buildings, houses, roads, and other developments) as land cover types.

Spatio-temporal analysis of the ecosystem health of Boracay Island

The VOR (vigor-organization-resilience) method of ecosystem health (EH) assessment employs the parameters of ecosystem vigor (EV), ecosystem organization (EO), and ecosystem resilience (ER) (Wang et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Li et al., 2023; Lei et al., 2023; Costanza, 2012). Ecosystem Health is calculated as follow (Li et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022):

$$EH = \sqrt[3]{EV \times EO \times ER}$$

where EH is ecosystem health, EV is ecosystem vigor, EO is ecosystem organization, and ER is ecosystem resilience. The EH values is a linear scale value of 0 to 1, where 0 represents the “weakest” EH and 1 represents the “best” EH (Das et al., 2020). The ecosystem health values will be categorized into five using an equal-interval approach (Cheng et al., 2018): degraded (0 to 0.2), unhealthy (0.2 to 0.4), average health (0.4 to 0.6), suboptimal health (0.6 to 0.8), and highest health (0.8 to 1.0) (He et al., 2019). Description of each index value of ecosystem health is presented in Table 2.

- **Ecosystem Vigor (EV)**

Ecosystem vigor is the measure of activity and metabolism or primary productivity. It is the ecological metabolism and nutrient recycling capacity of

an ecosystem (Chen et al., 2016; Ge et al., 2022). It is determined from the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI). NDVI positively correlates with vegetation production and as such, has been widely used to measure EV (Wang et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023). The range of NDVI is [-1, 1], where the closer absolute value to 1 has the greatest EV (Li et al., 2023). The formula for calculating NDVI is:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - R}{NIR + R}$$

where NIR and R are the fourth and third bands, respectively, of Landsat TM images and fourth and fifth bands, respectively, of Landsat OLI images (Wang et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023).

- **Ecosystem Organization (EO)**

It denotes the complexity and stability of the ecosystem and is measured using landscape indices related to landscape fragmentation/heterogeneity (LF/LH), landscape connectivity (LC), and landscape shape (LS) (Wang et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023). Referring to previous studies (He et al., 2019; Li et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022; Ge et al., 2022; and Karimi and Raymond, 2022), SHDI and SHEI are selected for LF/LH, to quantify landscape diversity as used by Karimi and Raymond (2022) in their study titled, "*Assessing the diversity and evenness of ecosystem services as perceived by residents using participatory mapping*". In their study, they used both SHDI and SHEI in quantifying spatial patterns of the perceived ecosystem services at the landscape scale which shows the richness of the mapped ecosystem service types and equitability in abundance of the ecosystem services. Furthermore, AI, COHESION, CONTAG, and DIVISION are selected for LC, and AWFDI and AWMSI are

selected for LS (see Table 3 for the landscape indices and their ecological significance). The *Fragstats* software was used to calculate the landscape indices for each period. The weight of each parameter and sub-parameters are assigned using analytical hierarchy process, AHP (Wang et al., 2022; Goepel, 2018) with inputs referenced from Wang et al (2022) and Li et al (2023). The AHP is a ratio scale method that is used to assist in decision making such as in natural resource and environmental management (Zhu and Dale, 2001).

$$EO = 0.715*LF + 0.187*LC + 0.098*LS$$

$$EO = (0.416*SHDI + 0.299*SHEI) + (0.101*CONTAG + 0.023*AI + 0.023*COHESION + 0.041*DIVISION) + (0.075*AWFDI + 0.023*AWMSI)$$

- **Ecosystem Resilience (ER)**

It is the ability of the landscape elements, such as the patches to maintain their function, structure, and service when subjected to natural and anthropogenic factors (Ge et al., 2022; Yu and Xiao, 2018). Ge et al (2022) pointed out that ER represents the resistance and adaptability of the landscape patches to external interferences of ecosystems. Land use/land cover is an indispensable influence on ecosystem recovery. Moreover, those land cover types that are characteristically closer to natural ecosystems can easier recover when subjected to external forces than those that are not (Ge et al., 2022). As such, natural land covers have higher resilience coefficient (RC).

ER was quantified from the sum of the area-weighted ecosystem resilience coefficients of all the land use/land cover types are identified (He et al., 2019). Ecosystem resilience is calculated for each land use based on Wang et al (2020) as:

$$ER = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i \times RC_i$$

where A_i is the area ratio of ecosystem type i and RC_i is the resilience coefficient of ecosystem type i , and n is the number of ecosystem type. Resilience coefficients of the various land cover types in Boracay Island, such as the built-up areas, forestlands, and water bodies are presented in Table 4. These RC values were adapted from previous studies of He et al (2019), Wang et al (2020), Wang et al (2022), and Li et al (2023).

IX. RESULTS

A. Spatio-temporal changes in the land cover of Boracay Island

Figure 5. Temporal change of landscape structure of Boracay Island, Philippines.

Land cover types identified from Landsat images taken at different time periods are built-up areas (in red), vegetation (in green), and waterbodies, which are either wetlands or portion of the coast (in blue). The land cover maps generated for each period is presented in Figure 5. During the early years of tourism in the island up until the present, built-up areas has sprawled the island, wherein there are no apparent signatures noted in 1989 images to 35.2% of the landscape covered by structures.

Vegetation cover has decreased from 94.5%, to 62.3%, and waterbodies from 5.5% to 2.4%.

Figure 6. Graph of temporal changes of the landscape structure of Boracay Island.

B. Spatio-temporal changes in ecosystem health of Boracay Island

During the early years of the island's tourism, forestlands and waterbodies dominated the landscape. As tourism has brought in more businesses, forestlands were converted to commercial and residential zones, hence the increased in the built-up areas. Figure 7 shows the changes in the ecosystem vigor of the island. Highly productive areas (green) correspond to forestland and other vegetated areas in the landscape. Yellow to yellow green areas correspond to built-up areas and wetlands. Red to orange areas correspond to wetlands and portions of coastal areas. Vigor of the island deteriorates from highly productive (0.80 to 1.00) in areas of vegetated land covers to moderately productive (0.40 to 0.60) in built-up areas and waterbodies.

Ecosystem organization was determined using different metrics of landscape structure to analyze the heterogeneity, connectivity, and shape of the landscape of Boracay Island. Landscape heterogeneity or fragmentation of the island shows more than one patch type present and the proportion are distributed and fragmented where from 1989 to 2020, the increasing value of SHDI and SHEI indicates that the landscape has become more fragmented. In terms of its landscape connectivity, the landscape has become more disaggregated, as shown by the decreasing AI, patches more divided, indicated by increasing DIVISION values, and unevenly distributed, as noted by the decreasing CONTAG. The shape of the landscape elements has become more complex and irregular as indicated by the increasing values of FRAC_AM and SHAPE_AM. Over all, the ecosystem organization of the island is decreasing, i.e., becoming fragmented, discontinuous, and irregularly complex.

Figure 7. Changes in the ecosystem vigor of Boracay Island from 1989 to 2020.

Figure 8. Result of the landscape metric analysis of Boracay Island for each barangay from 1989 to 2020.

Figure 9. Ecosystem organization of Boracay Island from the analyses of the landscape metrics.

The ecosystem resilience was obtained from landscape pattern analysis and the resilience coefficient of the land cover identified. The resilience of the landscape has been decreasing from 1989 to 2020 for all the barangays of Boracay Island. As more forestlands and vegetated areas are being converted to built-up areas, e.g., to residential areas and tourist economic zones, the resilience of the landscape diminishes and becomes more vulnerable to natural and anthropogenic disturbances.

Figure 10. Ecosystem resilience of Boracay Island from landscape metrics and the resilience coefficient.

Figure 11. Spatio-temporal changes of ecosystem health of Boracay Island from 1989 to 2020.

The changes in the levels of ecosystem health of Boracay Island for each barangay showed significant changes since 1989. Figure 9 shows the spatio-temporal changes from 1989 to 2020. Initially, the landscape has suboptimal healthy ecosystem (0.6 – 0.8). It has moderate level of structural integrity, stability, and sustainability, high ecological function, slight negative impact from external human and/or non-human factors, no abnormalities, and moderate resilience. In 2000, Barangays Balabag and Manocmanoc have unhealthy to average healthy ecosystem while Barangay Yapak

has an average healthy to suboptimal healthy ecosystem. In 2018, the year Boracay Island was closed for rehabilitation, the ecosystem health level changed to unhealthy for Barangays Balabag and Manocmanoc and average health for Barangay Yapak. In 2020, Barangay Manocmanoc has unhealthy to degraded ecosystem health, Barangay Balabag has unhealthy ecosystem health, and Barangay Yapak maintained its average healthy ecosystem. From 1989 to 2020, ecosystem health deteriorated by 57.6% in Barangay Manocmanoc, by 47.4% in Barangay Balabag, and 19.6% in Barangay Yapak.

Figure 12. Graph of the change in ecosystem health of Boracay Island from 1989 to 2020.

X. DISCUSSION

Health as a concept is mostly referred medically, such as to indicate the state of the human body, but at recent years, has been slowly being used in animal and plant research (Ge et al., 2022). World Health Organization (n.d.) defines this concept as a state of “complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not only the absence of disease or infirmity”. The living environment has undergone changes based upon the developments on socio-economy and culture (Ge et al., 2022). Ge et al (2022) further enumerated the changes in the living environments such as global warming and climate change, extreme rainfall, increased carbon dioxide in the atmosphere, soil erosion, urbanization, salinization of freshwater, reduction of wetlands, eutrophication of water bodies, and loss of biodiversity. Due to this, the concept of health has shifted into the context of the environment and as such, ecosystem health was proposed and provides a fundamental theoretical basis for land use planning and ecosystem management (Ge et al., 2022).

In the case of Boracay Island, where the rapid growth of tourism industry has reached to a point where the massive development and utilization of the island’s natural resources have become incompatible with the supposed appropriate uses as prescribed by environmental policies governing the island, such as the Proclamation No. 1064 (2006) which classifies Boracay Island into forestland for protection purposes and agricultural land (alienable and disposable). These developments have resulted to various environmental problems such as flooding in low-lying areas, water pollution, salt water intrusion, deterioration of air quality, noise pollution, improper solid waste disposal, exploitation of caves and cave resources, loss of biodiversity and damage to habitat of wildlife, illegal reclamation and occupation of wetlands, illegal occupation/squatting in forestlands by residential and commercial establishments,

excessive load on the carrying capacity of the island, increasing generation of toxic wastes (Boracay Environment Master Plan 2008 – 2033, 2008).

Figure 13. Patches of hotel establishments within the forestland area of Mt. Luho in Brgy. Balabag. Photo taken last 2019.

The use of remote sensing data has proven to be a cost-effective alternative in the monitoring and assessing landscape structure and ecosystem health across space and time, hence, this together with geographic information system have been widely used in ecosystem health assessments (Wang et al., 2020). The use of free satellite images such as of that of Landsat developed and managed by National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the United States Geological Survey (USGS) allows researchers to quickly assess space-time distribution and evolution of landscape structure and ecosystem health of areas of interests (Wang et al., 2020; USGS, n.d.).

The ecosystem health is reflective of the overall state of a landscape (Wang et al., 2020). Ecosystem health assessment is generally complex as it deals with complex

ecosystems, as such, many model evaluation methods were developed (Ge et al., 2022). Specific to assessment of the health of ecosystem structure, VOR method is usually employed. Assessment of the landscape structure through landscape metrics provides the initial input in assessing ecosystem health. In fact, landscape patterns are a significant indicator of change in ecosystem health as it signifies the natural state of ecosystem and influencing their organization and function (Li et al., 2023). Boracay Island's ecosystem health showed a deteriorating trend as tourism grow in the island. All of the three barangays in Boracay Island have a generally decreasing ecosystem health where from suboptimal healthy state of the landscape have become an average healthy to unhealthy ecosystems. Most of the developments in the island are concentrated in Barangay Balabag, located in the saddle portion of Boracay, and Barangay Manocmanoc. In these barangays, vegetated areas have become mostly fragmented due to infrastructure development. On the other hand, Barangay Yapak has deteriorated ecosystem health from suboptimal health to average health where substantial large patches of forestlands are still present. The three barangay has the same rate of EHI deterioration from 1989 to 2000, i.e., 14.70% in Brgy. Yapak, 19% in Brgy. Manocmanoc, and 21% in Brgy. Balabag. However, from 2000 to 2020, Brgy. Yapak's ecosystem health deterioration slowed down by less than 1% (2000 to 2018) to 4.4% (2018 to 2020) as compared to Brgy. Balabag and Manocmanoc where the rate of deterioration of ecosystem health ranges from 14% to 24%.

Figure 14. Area in Brgy. Yapak previously occupied by Boracay Ecovillage Resort and Convention Center. After the hotel was closed around 2018 to 2019, the vegetation proliferated in the area through natural regeneration. Photo taken last 2022.

Figure 15 shows the spatio-temporal changes of the landscape structure of Boracay Island from 1989 to 2020. This shows that most of built-up areas are located in Brgy. Balabag, (128.34 ha) as compared to Brgy. Manocmanoc (128.7 ha). However, the ecosystem health of Balabag is higher than that Manocmanoc. Comparing the two barangays, Brgy. Balabag has more aggregated and less divided forestland such as the Mt. Luho where two wetlands are within its vicinities. Brgy. Manocmanoc has a more fragmented, discontinuous, and irregular vegetated area. In summary, ecosystem health of Boracay is healthy at the portions where vegetated land cover is less fragmented, more aggregated and less discontinuous, and less complex, whereas ecosystem health is unhealthy to degraded in areas that are more fragmented, disaggregated, and complex. Unhealthy to degraded ecosystem health are in areas with the most development. In 2020, Brgy. Yapak has an average healthy EH, Brgy. Balabag has a unhealthy EH, and Brgy. Manocmanoc has a unhealthy to degraded EH.

Figure 15. (Top photo) Coastal area of Boracay Island lined and dominated by coconut trees and other vegetation (Gomez, 2019). (Bottom photo) Establishments line up the coastal area of the island. This portion of the White Beach is along Station 1 Grotto. The bottom photo was taken last 2018.

XI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In this study, the ecosystem health of Boracay Island in 1989, 2000, 2018, and 2020 was evaluated based on the parameters of VOR method developed by Costanza (1992): ecosystem vigor, ecosystem organization, and ecosystem resilience. This study analyzed the spatial and temporal changes of ecosystem health level of the barangays in the island based on the changes in the landscape structure using Landsat images. The results of this study are summarized as follows:

- The land cover types identified in Boracay Island are built-up areas, vegetation/forestland, and waterbodies. The overall landscape of Boracay Island has changed since the years of tourism up to the present, from 1989 to 2020. Vegetation cover diminished by 94.4% in 1989 to 62.3% in 2020 while built-up areas sprawled the island where initially it covers 15% in 2020 and have grown to 35.2% in 2020. Figure 3 shows the spatial distribution and temporal changes of the land cover types of Boracay Island from 1989 to 2020.
- The ecosystem health parameters, such as vigor, organization, and resilience were evaluated from processing of NDVI from Landsat images for the ecosystem vigor, weighted landscape metrics of fragmentation/heterogeneity, connectivity, and patch shape for ecosystem organization, and land cover area and resilience coefficient of the land cover for the ecosystem resilience.
- Ecosystem vigor shows that the landscape of Boracay Island deteriorates in productivity from high to very high productivity in 1989 to 2000 to high to moderate productivity from 2018 to 2020. Generally, areas covered by forestlands, vegetated areas, and open spaces with limited development has

high to very high productivity, whereas areas with built-up sprawling and high density of development has moderate productivity.

- The ecosystem organization shows that the landscape of the island has become fragmented, disaggregated, divided, and complex at present with developments brought by tourism growth from a less heterogenous, more aggregated, and less complex landscape comprising only mostly of vegetation and wetlands.
- The ecosystem resilience of Boracay Island has been decreasing from 1989 to 2020 for all its barangays. The conversion of vegetated areas into built zones diminishes the resilience of the landscape which makes it more vulnerable to natural and anthropogenic disturbances.
- The resulting ecosystem health level of Boracay Island has evolved from suboptimal health conditions in 1989 to mostly average health with patches of suboptimal and average healthy ecosystems in 2000. In 2018, the island evolved into average healthy to unhealthy landscape.

With the foregoing results of this study, the following are proposed:

- Formulate policies that promotes an average to healthy ecosystem health level such that the overall landscape structure of Boracay Island becomes less fragmented, more aggregated vegetated areas, and less complex patches. The Local Government of Malay should review zoning and land use plans of the municipality and must update these, incorporating relevant institutions governing the environment and natural resources of Boracay Island such as the PD 1064 wherein forestland or timberland are strictly for protection purposes and parcels within the A&D are the only ones designated for development. This

way areas in the island that are intended for protection can be rehabilitated and restored;

- For the hotels, establishments, and residential owners, promote green infrastructure in their properties, such as installing vertical garden, green roofing, etc. This will mimic the processes in a natural ecosystem that promotes carbon sequestration, improve air quality, and protects biodiversity;
- For the DENR, enforce and conduct extensive, interdisciplinary environmental impact assessment for any developments, resulting to land cover changes affecting protection areas under PD 1064 are concerned;
- For the DENR CENRO Boracay and the LGU of Malay, enforce the existing environmental laws governing Boracay Island, such as PD 1064, PD 1586, RA 9275, RA 9003, RA 8749, and other local ordinances on environmental protection of the Municipality of Malay.

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APPENDICES

Table 1. Results of the landscape pattern analysis for the evaluation of ecosystem organization for each barangay of Boracay Island.

	Landscape fragmentation		Landscape Connectivity				Landscape Shape		EO	Normalized EO
	SHDI	SHEI	AI	COHESION	DIVISION	CONTAG	SHAPE_AM	FRAC_AM		
2020										
Yapak	0.696	0.633	83.373	98.427	0.485	47.336	5.980	1.243	9.722	0.318
Balabag	0.758	0.690	79.073	97.211	0.665	40.850	5.102	1.233	8.965	0.167
Manocmanoc	0.777	0.708	75.258	97.791	0.737	37.567	6.813	1.267	8.625	0.100
2018										
Yapak	0.664	0.604	85.052	98.066	0.431	50.073	4.891	1.212	9.971	0.368
Balabag	0.723	0.658	83.994	97.648	0.592	46.445	4.493	1.209	9.607	0.295
Manocmanoc	0.741	0.674	78.795	97.499	0.658	41.998	5.534	1.236	9.081	0.191
2000										
Yapak	0.700	0.637	87.036	98.002	0.423	49.356	4.265	1.196	9.949	0.363
Balabag	0.693	0.631	86.018	97.634	0.429	48.966	3.964	1.193	9.865	0.346
Manocmanoc	0.638	0.581	85.764	97.493	0.360	51.694	3.871	1.186	10.087	0.391
1989										
Yapak	0.208	0.300	96.866	98.602	0.105	77.683	1.657	1.068	12.649	0.900
Balabag	0.204	0.294	95.534	98.743	0.100	76.616	2.128	1.103	12.526	0.876
Manocmanoc	0.227	0.328	94.517	98.518	0.117	73.377	2.295	1.114	12.196	0.810

SHDI	Equals $SHDI = 0$ when only one patch is present and increases, without limit, as the number of classes increases while the proportions are equally distributed
SHEI	Equals $SHEI = 0$ when only one patch present and equals $SHEI = 1$ when the proportion of classes is completely equally distributed
AI	Equals 0 for maximally disaggregated and 100 for maximally aggregated classes.
CONTAG	Approaches $CONTAG = 0$ if all cells are unevenly distributed and 100 indicates that all cells are equally adjacent to all other classes.
DIVISION	Equals $DIVISION = 0$ if only one patch is present. Approaches $DIVISION = 1$ if all patches of class i are single cells.
SHAPE_AM	Equals $SHAPE_MN = 1$ if all patches are squares. Increases, without limit, as the shapes of patches become more complex.
FRAC_AM	Approaches $FRAC_MN = 1$ if all patches are squared and $FRAC_MN = 2$ if all patches are irregular.

Table 2. Computations of ecosystem resilience using landscape metric and resilience coefficient.

	Yapak		CA	RC	ER per patch type	ΣER
		2020	Built	103.59	0.2	
	Forest	279.99	0.6	167.994		
	Water	11.16	0.7	7.812		
2020	Balabag		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Built	128.34	0.2	25.668	138.681
		Forest	181.53	0.6	108.918	
		Water	5.85	0.7	4.095	
	Manocmanoc		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Built	128.7	0.2	25.74	136.971
		Forest	176.67	0.6	106.002	
Water		7.47	0.7	5.229		
2018	Yapak		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Built	82.71	0.2	16.542	205.236
		Forest	297.27	0.6	178.362	
		Water	14.76	0.7	10.332	
	Balabag		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Built	114.12	0.2	22.824	144.234
		Forest	197.1	0.6	118.26	
		Water	4.5	0.7	3.15	
	Manocmanoc		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Built	103.14	0.2	20.628	147.231
		Forest	201.87	0.6	121.122	
		Water	7.83	0.7	5.481	
2000	Yapak		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Built	67.23	0.2	13.446	212.778
		Forest	299.25	0.6	179.55	
		Water	28.26	0.7	19.782	
	Balabag		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Built	60.21	0.2	12.042	167.148
		Forest	237.51	0.6	142.506	
		Water	18	0.7	12.6	
	Manocmanoc		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Built	35.37	0.2	7.074	176.283

		Forest	250.2	0.6	150.12	
		Water	27.27	0.7	19.089	
1989	Yapak		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Forest	373.77	0.6	224.262	238.941
		Water	20.97	0.7	14.679	
	Balabag		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Forest	299.34	0.6	179.604	191.07
		Water	16.38	0.7	11.466	
	Manocmanoc		CA	RC	ER per patch type	
		Forest	294.03	0.6	176.418	189.585
		Water	18.81	0.7	13.167	

Table 3. Descriptive statistical analysis of ecosystem health index per barangay from 1989 to 2020.

	Barangay	Count	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Sum	SD	Variance
1989	Balabag	3407	0.3412	0.7883	0.6876	2342.5416	0.0375	0.0014
	Manocmanoc	3321	0.3582	0.7450	0.7182	2385.0185	0.0378	0.0014
	Yapak	4219	0.3819	0.7907	0.7671	3236.3989	0.0440	0.0019

	Barangay	Count	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Sum	SD	Variance
2000	Balabag	1869	0.2409	0.6018	0.4480	837.2585	0.0370	0.0014
	Manocmanoc	1602	0.2337	0.5162	0.4892	783.7681	0.0274	0.0007
	Yapak	2099	0.2723	0.6055	0.5704	1197.3158	0.0404	0.0016

	Barangay	Count	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Sum	SD	Variance
2018	Balabag	3104	0.1816	0.5940	0.3290	1021.0785	0.0426	0.0018
	Manocmanoc	2955	0.1981	0.3444	0.2938	868.0356	0.0163	0.0003
	Yapak	4146	0.2614	0.5947	0.5630	2334.2873	0.0414	0.0017

	Barangay	Count	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Sum	SD	Variance
2020	Balabag	2723	0.0000	0.5440	0.2451	667.3373	0.0464	0.0022
	Manocmanoc	2212	0.0000	0.2504	0.1930	426.8907	0.0125	0.0002
	Yapak	4137	0.0000	0.5455	0.5156	2132.8388	0.0434	0.0019

Table 4. Summary of the average ecosystem health index per barangay from 1989 to 2020.

Barangay	2020	2018	2000	1989
Balabag	0.2451	0.3290	0.4480	0.6876
Manocmanoc	0.1930	0.2938	0.4892	0.7182
Yapak	0.5156	0.5630	0.5704	0.7671
AVERAGE	0.3179	0.3952	0.5025	0.7243

Table 5. Changes of ecosystem health for each interval period of Boracay Island (in percentage).

BARANGAYS	2020-2018	2018-2000	2000-1989	2020-1989
Balabag	14.61	15.32	21.10	47.4
Manocmanoc	20.70	24.97	18.96	57.6
Yapak	4.40	0.65	14.70	19.6